

Exploring and Analyzing the Potential of Sustainable Control Strategies of Fusarium Wilt in Northeastern Egypt

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Abstract:- *Fusarium oxysporum*, one of the most soil-borne fungi causes damage to a wide range of economical crops worldwide. This research was conducted as a complimentary part of the first report for detecting the presence of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *albedinis* (Foa) in North Sinai and to compare the alternative eco-friendly control procedures with commercial products to keep the environment at a minimal level of pollution. *F. oxysporum* isolates were collected from the four main coastline regions in North Sinai from clearly symptomatic date trees with wilt, drying, chlorosis, and progressive dieback. The study was applied based on the previous molecular characterization by specific primers test for detecting Foa (FOA₁-BIO₃ & FOA₂₈-TL₃). There were only 13 isolates amplified with the primer (FOA₂₈-TL₃) had been chosen to apply the study. The efficacy of three tested fungicides (Rizolex-T, Tachigaren, and Dithane M-45) varied in decreasing the hyphal growth rate. Tachigaren at concentration 500 and 1000 ppm showed high inhibited growth 65 % and 51 % respectively of the *Fusarium* tested isolates in vitro than other fungicides. The biological agents: *Trichoderma album* was the significant inhibitor for the *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates, it showed highly competitive and suppressive growth against all *Fusarium* isolates, the range of mycelial inhibition percentage (PGI) was about 75% on average followed by *T. Harzianum* was 73% on average, moreover, *T. strigosum* was 71.5% on average. *Bacillus subtilis* showed significant inhibition for the growth of *Fusarium* isolates in range of 40% on average but the *Bacillus megaterium* did not show any significant action against most isolates.

Keywords:- Bayoud, Biological Agents, *Fusarium*, Environment, Phylogenetic, Fungicides, Sinai.

I. INTRODUCTION

Date palms in Egypt are cultivated thousands of years, despite its roles in Egyptian economy and daily life, although the efforts are being made periodically, date palm industry, production, processing, and marketing faced beleaguered with several problems [1]. The low quality of products and farm management accompanied with insufficient applicable research are the major obstacles of

the date palm production in Egypt Riad [2]. Egypt has around 127 thousand acre and produce around 2.2 million tones [3]. *Fusarium oxysporum* is a soilborne fungal pathogen that causes wilt diseases in a wide range of plants, including date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*). It is one of the most destructive date palm diseases, causing significant economic losses to growers worldwide [4]. Many *Fusarium* spp. infects date palm such as *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *Albedinis*, *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *canariensis*, *F. proliferatum*, *F. solan*. The fungus enters the plant through the roots and colonizes the vascular system and causes severe damage and stops water and nutrient route from the root. This leads to wilting and trees loss [5]. Mancozeb is a wide-spectrum contact fungicide that can be used on a variety of fruits, vegetables, and field crops for its ability to provide protection against many pathogens. The Fungicide Resistance Action Committee (FRAC) has classed mancozeb. It disrupts various metabolic processes within the fungal cell cytoplasm and mitochondria by interfering with enzymes containing sulphhydryl groups [6]. Hymexazol (HYM), a prominent fungicide utilized against soilborne pathogens, undergoes conversion into glycoside metabolites and subsequently undergoes glycosylation with amino sugars. This process results in the production of glycosylated compounds that exhibit a wide range of biological activities, mimicking the glycosylation processes observed in plants. *Bacillus* strains generally exhibit their capacity to regulate biological systems through the predominant inhibition of plant pathogens' growth, as well as the induction of systemic resistance in plants and engagement in ecological competition for habitats with plants [7, 8]. *Trichoderma* species have been extensively utilized in agricultural settings due to their well-established mechanism of biological control [9]. Using *Trichoderma* spp. as biological control for pea seed damping-off that induced by a *Pythium* sp. and *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *cucumerinum* showed highly competitive for nutrients (Nitrogen and Carbon) and there were observed mycoparasitic interaction in dual culture [10].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Fungal Source:

The study was conducted in four different cities in North Sinai (Rafah, Al Shaikh Zewayed, Al Arish, and Bear Al-Abd) to identify the causal pathogen of foliar symptoms for Hayany, Samany, Bent Easha, and Madjhoor varieties. The macroscopic, microscopic, and phylogenetic characterizations were conducted on a group of representative isolates for the four regions, additionally, this study was done on thirteen isolates that amplified with the specific primers for detecting *Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. albedinis* (Foa) to investigate the best management protocol instead of fungicides [6].

B. *Fusarium Control*:

➤ *Effect of Chemical Fungicides on Fusarium oxysporum Isolates Mycelial Linear Growth in Vitro.*

The effects of three fungicides (**Table 1**) were assayed by using the poisoned food technique according to the method described by Abdalla *et al.* [11]. Fungicides were added to autoclaved PDA medium before dispensing medium in Petri plates at different concentrations (10, 50, 100, 500, and 1000 ppm) when the temperature of the medium was about 50°C. The control treatment was PDA medium without additions. Disks 5mm in diameter from 7 days of cultures of the tested fungi were transferred to the center of Petri plates and incubated at 27±2°C. After the 7-, 10- and 14-day incubation period, the linear growth of the tested fungi was recorded.

Table 1 Trade Name, Chemical Constitutions, Formulation Type, Active Ingredient(s), Recommended Concentration in the Field, and Arab Republic of Egypt Registration No. of Fungicides were used to Control *Fusarium oxysporum* Isolates.

No.	Trade name	Chemical constitutions	Formulation Type	Active ingredient(s)	Recommended concentration in the field	ARE Registration No.
1	Rizolex-T	20% O, O-Dimethyl-o-(2,6-dichloro-4-methylphenyl) phosphor-thioate+30% Bis (dimethylthiocarbamonyl) disulfide.	50 % WP	Tolclofos-methyl Thiram	3 gm/kg seeds	07
2	Tachigaren	5-methylisoxazol-3-ol	30% SL	Hymexazol	1 ml / 1 L	780
3	Dithane M-45	Manganese Ethylenebis (dithiocarbamate) (polymeric) complex with zinc salt	80 % WP	Mancozeb	2.5 gm / 1 L	189

➤ *Antagonistic Activity of Microorganisms Against Fusarium oxysporum Isolates:*

• *Antagonistic Activity of Trichoderma Album Against Fusarium oxysporum Isolates:*

✓ *Source of Antagonist:*

The *Trichoderma album* isolate was isolated from the commercial biological control formula “Bio Zeid” which was kindly provided by Pro. Dr. Nagi M. Abou Zeid Plant Pathology Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza.

✓ *Interaction between Trichoderma Album and Fusarium oxysporum:*

The biological control agents were tested against *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates in vitro using potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium in 9 cm diameter Petri plates. A five mm diameter disc of a seven-day-old fungal growth of the tested *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates was placed two cm from the edge of the plate. On the opposite side of the Petri plate, a five mm disc of the tested antagonistic fungus was placed. Plates were fermented at 25°C and kept under daily observation and data were recorded one week later as liner growth of the *Fusarium oxysporum* cultures [2, 12].

• *Antagonistic Activity of Trichoderma strigosum and Trichoderma harzianum Against Fusarium oxysporum Isolates:*

✓ *Source of Antagonist:*

One gram of dry soil from each sample was added to test tubes containing 9 ml of sterile water. Each test tube was shaken periodically for approximately 15 minutes. After shaking one ml of suspension, it was added to the tube containing 9 ml sterile water, and the process was repeated to make serial dilutions up to 1:10000 for each fungal isolation. Aliquots of 1 ml of serial dilutions were spread on APDA plates. All plates were fermented at 25°C. After 2-7 days the isolated microorganisms from the rhizosphere were identified according to their morphological characters. The antagonistic fungi were identified at the Unit of Identification of Microorganisms, Plant Pathology Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, using BIOLOG TM system.

✓ *Interaction between Trichoderma strigosum, Trichoderma harzianum, and Fusarium oxysporum:*

The experiment proceeded in Petri plates filled with 15 ml sterilized PDA, and five mm diameter discs of each bioagent culture were placed at a 2 cm distance from the edge of the Petri dishes, whereas the opposite side of the plates was inoculated with a similar disc of *Fusarium oxysporum*. Three plates were used for each antagonist.

Control plates contained only the test fungus (*Fusarium oxysporum*). All plates were fermented at 27±2°C.

• *Antagonistic Activity of Bacillus megaterium Against Fusarium oxysporum Isolate:*

✓ *Source of Antagonist:*

The *Bacillus megaterium* culture was isolated from the commercial biological control formula “Bio Arc” which was kindly provided by Pro. Dr. Nagi M. Abou Zeid Plant Pathology Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza.

✓ *Interaction between Bacillus megaterium and Fusarium oxysporum:*

The bacterium was maintained on a PDA medium at 33±2°C. The *Bacillus megaterium* isolate was tested against *Fusarium oxysporum* using PDA medium in 9 cm diameter Petri plates. 5 mm diameter discs of the tested fungus were placed two cm from the edge of the plate. On the opposite side of the Petri plates at about 2 cm from the edge, a streak of the tested antagonistic bacterium was placed as suggested by [2]. PDA dishes were inoculated with discs 5 mm in diameter of *F. oxysporum* at the center and were kept as control. All treatments were repeated four times and were incubated at 33±2°C. Observations were daily till the control dishes were completely colonized by *F. oxysporum*.

• *Antagonistic Activity of Bacillus subtilis Against Fusarium oxysporum Isolates:*

✓ *Source of Antagonist:*

The *Bacillus subtilis* culture was isolated from the commercial biological control formula called “Clean Root” which was kindly provided by the Central Laboratory of

Organic Agriculture (CLOA) - Agricultural Research Center, Giza.

✓ *Interaction between Bacillus subtilis and Fusarium oxysporum:*

The bacterium was maintained on a PDA medium at 33±2°C. The *Bacillus subtilis* isolate was tested against *Fusarium oxysporum* using PDA medium in 9 cm diameter petri plates. 5 mm diameter discs of the tested fungus were placed two cm from the edge of the plate. On the opposite side of the Petri plates at about 2 cm from the edge, a streak of the tested antagonistic bacterium was placed [2]. PDA dishes were inoculated with discs 5 mm in diameter of *F. oxysporum* at the center and were kept as control. All treatments were carried out four times and were incubated at 33±2°C.

Observations were carried out daily till the control dishes were completely colonized by *F. oxysporum*.

After one week, plates were then examined and linear growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* was determined. The percent growth inhibition was calculated as per the formula given below by Nikam *et al.* [13].

▪ *Data Analysis:*

All experiments were conducted in a completely randomized design (CRD). Mean values were compared by the least

significant difference (LSD) testing at $p = 0.05$. All statistical analyses were performed using Co-STAT software V.6.13 (CoHort software, Berkeley, CA 94701). Also, EC50 uses LDP-Line and GW-BASIC (Version 3.23 from Microsoft®).

$$\text{Percent growth inhibition (PGI)} = \frac{\text{Colony growth in control plate} - (\text{Colony growth in intersection plate})}{(\text{Colony growth in control plate})} \times 100$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

❖ *Fusarium Control:*

A. *Effect of Chemical Fungicides on Mycelial Linear Growth of Fusarium oxysporum Isolates in Vitro.*

In these experiments, the fungitoxic effects of the tested fungicides against the hyphal growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates were recorded in Table 2. The following data were illustrated as Percent Growth Inhibition (PGI) and the EC₅₀ which is a value that represents the amount of active ingredient of the chemical in milligrams used to inhibit 50% of the fungal growth. Data presented in Table 2 explained that the fungicide Tachigaren 30% SL was more effective in controlling the radial growth of *F. oxysporum* isolates than other fungicides, followed by Rizolex-T 50% WP and Dithane M-45 80% WP. It caused the highest inhibition percentage (PGI) of 92.2%, 88.6%, and 80% to isolate I₂, A₅, and G₁ respectively at 1000 ppm and 75.6%,

65.6%, and 61.1% to isolate I₂, G₁, H₁, and A₅ respectively at 500 ppm. Finally, it caused the lowest significant inhibition at 100 ppm with 57.8%, 51.1, and 47.8% for I₂, F₄₅, and A₅ isolates compared with Rizolex-T 50% and Dithane M-45 80%. Tachigaren's (Hymexazol) high efficacy is due to its interference with fungal RNA and DNA synthesis; it is swiftly translocated and has local systemic distribution properties. When hymexazol enters a plant, it is swiftly converted into glucosides. The O-glucoside has fungitoxic activity on pathogenic fungi. Whereas the N-glucoside has been associated with certain plant growth-promoting effects [14]. The mode of action of fungicide Tachigaren 30% SL leads to effectively destroying membrane permeability in pathogens. There is often a decrease in mycelial weight, increased protein leakage, reduced glucose uptake, and morphological changes in the hyphae accompanied by protoplasmic bursting Shoji [15-20].

Table 2 Recommended concentrations of three fungicides “Tachigaren, Rizolex-T, and Dithane M-45” for inhibiting the expansion of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates (A₅, B₁, B₇, C₁, C₂₄, D₂, F₄₅, F₄₈, F₅₃, F₅₈, H₁, G₁ and I₂) *in vitro* after 14 days of incubation.

Fungal isolate*	Treatment	EC ₅₀ (ppm)**	A confidence level of Upper Conc. (ppm)	Confidence Level of Lower Conc. (ppm)	Slope
A ₅	Tachigaren 30% SL	126.37	172.28	92.69	0.875
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	609.78	1227.35	311.35	0.526
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	982.57	2384.82	422.49	0.486
B ₁	Tachigaren 30% SL	992.12	1534.19	644.96	1.00
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	> 1000 ppm	2840.21	1025.51	1.12
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	1968.07	1035.35	4.30
B ₇	Tachigaren 30% SL	> 1000 ppm	2031.64	802.27	1.05
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	> 1000 ppm	957881.60	3139.51	0.799
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	4566.56	2133.90	0.469
C ₁	Tachigaren 30% SL	588.22	674.98	512.60	2.92
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	678.32	784.18	586.80	2.79
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	1711.86	996.64	2.96
C ₂₄	Tachigaren 30% SL	318.67	444.06	229.66	0.932
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	> 1000 ppm	1221.34	847.91	3.03
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	2938.20	1183.66	1.54
D ₂	Tachigaren 30% SL	833.78	956.20	727.12	3.28
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	799.81	991.92	645.47	1.96
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	10834.18	1596.17	1.59
F ₄₅	Tachigaren 30% SL	107.33	174.86	64.80	0.530
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	513.75	586.06	450.32	3.21
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	5972.53	1415.51	0.977
F ₄₈	Tachigaren 30% SL	335.55	524.39	216.71	0.688
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	> 1000 ppm	6438.45	1335.90	0.469
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	57582.44	2720.97	0.687
F ₅₃	Tachigaren 30% SL	496.46	661.54	373.67	1.21
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	389.93	560.20	272.97	0.888
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	26367.60	2144.74	1.15
F ₅₈	Tachigaren 30% SL	302.57	497.56	186.10	0.601
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	840.29	1195.83	593.22	1.19
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	370.65	533.46	259.02	0.871
G ₁	Tachigaren 30% SL	363.36	420.00	310.88	2.57
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	733.05	1128.66	480.25	0.910
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	2566.53	2655.89	0.469
H ₁	Tachigaren 30% SL	402.78	488.98	331.97	1.77
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	578.50	798.60	420.49	1.12
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	4039.65	1295.13	2.15
I ₂	Tachigaren 30% SL	170.68	203.33	143.28	1.89
	Rizolex-T 50 % WP	376.41	446.81	317.17	2.06
	Dithane M-45 80 % WP	> 1000 ppm	15359	1085.91	2.10

* Origin of fungal isolates as following (A₅, B₁, B₇, C₁ and C₂₄) from Bear Al Abd and (D₂) from Rafah while (F₄₅, F₄₈, F₅₃, F₅₈, G₁, H₁ and I₂) from Al Arish.

** The EC₅₀ is the concentration value of which inhibited 50% of the fungal growth, *in vitro*.

B. Antagonistic Activity of Microorganisms Against *Fusarium oxysporum* Isolates:

➤ Antagonistic Activity of *Trichoderma* sp. Against *Fusarium oxysporum* Isolates:

Data presented in Table 3 and Plate 1 showed that *Trichoderma album* was significantly suppressive for the development of all *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates. It was highly competitive on APDA plates and it subsequently

mycoparasitized the mycelial growth of the pathogens. The range of mycelial inhibition percentage (PGI) is approximately 75%. But *Trichoderma strigosum* was significantly suppressive for the growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates and it subsequently mycoparasitized the mycelium growth of the pathogens. The range of mycelial inhibition percentage (PGI) from 71.57% to 87.04%. In the case of isolated F₄₅, *T. strigosum* was arrested for the growth of isolate F₄₅ without overgrowth. *Trichoderma harzianum*

was also significantly suppressive for the growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates (A₅, B₇, C₁, D₂, F₄₈, F₅₃, and H₁) and it subsequently mycoparasitized the mycelial expansion of the pathogens. The range of mycelial inhibition percentage (PGI) was 73.05% to 85.93%. But in the case of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates (B₁, C₂₄, F₄₅, F₅₈, G₁, and I₂) it significantly restricted the development of *F. oxysporum* isolates only without any overgrowth.

Biological control of plant disease may involve the use of beneficial microorganisms, such as specialized fungi, bacteria, and actinomycetes, to attack and control plant pathogens and the diseases they cause. The genus *Trichoderma* comprises many species some of which behave as biological control agents through one or more mechanisms. *Trichoderma* strains exert control against fungal phytopathogens indirectly by competing for nutrients and space, modifying the environmental condition, promoting plant growth, production of inhibitory compounds, plant defensive mechanisms, and antibiosis [21]. The antagonism occurs during interactions with other microorganisms involving low molecular weight diffusible volatile and nonvolatile toxic metabolite compounds [22] or antibiotics like harzianic acid, alamethicins, tricholin, peptaibols, antibiotics, 6-pentyl-pyrone, massoilactone, viridin, gliovirin, glisoprenins, heptelidic acid, and others. Mycoparasitism, the direct attack of biological agents on pathogens, is a very complex process that involves sequential events, including recognition, attack, subsequent penetration, and killing of pathogens. The cell wall degrading enzymes of *Trichoderma* such as different chitinolytic enzymes, glucanases, and proteases are considered important in mycoparasitism. Chitin and β -1, 3 glucans are the main structural components of the fungal cell wall. Chitinases, and β -1, 3 glucanases have been proposed as the key enzymes in the degradation of cell wall during mycoparasitism against phytopathogenic fungi [23].

➤ *Antagonistic Activity of Bacillus sp. Against Fusarium oxysporum Isolates:*

Data presented in Table 3 and Plate 1 showed that *Bacillus megaterium* did not significantly suppress the growth of *F. oxysporum* isolates. Inhibition zones were absent against *F. oxysporum* isolates except C₂₄ and F₄₅ in which the inhibition zone could be clearly shown. *Bacillus subtilis* was significantly suppressive for the growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates and the inhibitory rate was in the range of 34.82 – 41.11% except for isolate F₄₈.

The use of bacterial strains as biological control agents has received great attention because of the ability of such

strains to suppress different plant diseases involving a blend of diverse modes of action [24] and the possibility of being combined with other control methods. Among the most promising candidates for bacterial biocontrol agents are several species of the genus *Bacillus*, ubiquitously occurring safe microorganisms with proven excellent colonization aptitudes, versatility to protect plants effectively against pathogens, and an outstanding ability to sporulate, which assures their prevalence in the environment and guarantees future suitable formulation strategies [25]. According to Kilian *et al.* [26], the mechanisms of action that have so far been demonstrated experimentally for *Bacillus subtilis* include: a) competition in colonizing the rhizosphere and rhizoplane, b) production of antibiotic metabolites, c) induce resistance in plants by activation of defense genes, d) promotion of plant growth, especially root growth. Several *Bacillus* isolates have been natural factories of biologically active compounds, such as lipopeptides, and their contribution to plant microbial disease control is significant. Lipopeptides, oligopeptides synthesized in a non-ribosomal manner by large multienzyme complexes, are the most frequent antibiotic compounds produced by bacilli, exhibiting a wide antimicrobial spectrum and exceptional surfactant activities. The amphiphilic compounds discussed above exhibit a shared cyclic structure, which comprises a peptide moiety including a β -amino or β -hydroxy fatty acid. The main differences rely on the amino acid sequence and fatty acid branching, criteria that allow their classification into three families. The iturin family, comprising iturin A, mycosubtilin, and bacillomycin, consists of heptapeptides containing a β -amino fatty acid moiety, and is known for its potent antifungal properties. The fengycin family, along with its closely related variant plipastatin, comprises a group of decapeptides featuring a β -hydroxy fatty acid. These compounds exhibit distinctive characteristics, such as the inclusion of ornithine in the peptide segment, and demonstrate antifungal activities, albeit with a greater affinity for filamentous fungus [27]. The surfactin family, which has received significant attention in research, is comprised of heptapeptides that incorporate a β -hydroxy fatty acid with a carbon chain length typically ranging from 13 to 15. These lipopeptides are considered to be exceptionally potent biosurfactants and have been found to possess antiviral properties. While their antifungal activity is relatively modest, they exhibit a robust synergistic effect when combined with iturin A. Additionally, surfactin appears to play a crucial role in the creation of stable biofilms and may also hinder the formation of biofilms by other bacteria, hence contributing to its protective function [2, 12, 28-68].

Table 3 The antagonistic effect of *Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Trichoderma strigosum*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, and *Trichoderma album* against *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates growth (mm) in vitro after 9 days of incubation.

Origin of fungal isolates	Treatment	Main linear growth of <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> (mm)		
		Microorganism against <i>F. oxysporum</i>	Control	* PGI %
Fungal isolate "A5" from Bear Al Abd	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	12.33 j	90	86.30
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	12.66 j		85.93
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	22.33 e-h		75.18

	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	58.66 ab		34.82
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	52.33 d		41.86
Fungal isolate "B1" from Bear Al Abd	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	20.00 fgh	90	77.78
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	20.33 e-h		77.41
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	20.33 e-h		77.41
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	56.66 a-d		37.04
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	56.33 a-d		37.41
Fungal isolate "B7" from Bear Al Abd	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	21.50 e-h	90	76.11
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	22.66 e-h		74.82
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	23.33 e-h		74.17
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	56.33 a-d		37.41
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	54.66 bcd		39.35
Fungal isolate "C1" from Bear Al Abd	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	25.00 ef	90	72.22
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	22.00 e-h		75.65
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	22.33 e-h		75.27
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	57.00 a-d		36.75
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	53.00 cd		41.11
Fungal isolate "C24" from Bear Al Abd	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	21.33 e-h	90	76.30
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	20.33 e-h		77.41
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	21.33 e-h		76.30
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	52.66 d		41.57
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	54.66 bcd		39.35
Fungal isolate "D2" from Rafah	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	22.83 e-h	90	74.63
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	22.33 e-h		75.27
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	22.33 e-h		75.27
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	55.33 a-d		38.52
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	56.00 a-d		37.86
Fungal isolate "F45" from Al Arish	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	23.00 e-h	90	74.44
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	23.33 e-h		74.16
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	21.66 e-h		75.93
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	56.33 a-d		37.41
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	58.33 abc		68.52
Fungal isolate "F48" from Al Arish	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	23.33 e-h	90	74.16
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	23.00 e-h		74.44
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	23.00 e-h		74.44
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	54.33 bcd		39.63
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	54.66 bcd		39.35
Fungal isolate "F53" from Al Arish	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	25.66 e	90	71.57
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	24.33 efg		73.05
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	24.00 e-h		73.33
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	56.66 a-d		37.04
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	58.66 ab		34.82
Fungal isolate "F58" from Al Arish	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	19.33 ghi	90	78.52
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	23.66 e-h		73.71
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	19.33 ghi		78.52
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	53.33 bcd		40.74
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	57.00 a-d		36.75
Fungal isolate "G1" from Al Arish	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	14.00 ij	90	84.44
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	21.33 e-h		76.30
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	21.00 e-h		76.75
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	56.33 a-d		37.41
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	57.00 a-d		36.75

Continued Table 3: The antagonistic effect of *Bacillus megaterium*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Trichoderma strigosum*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, and *Trichoderma album* against *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates growth (mm) *in vitro* after 9 days of incubation.

Origin of fungal isolates	Treatment	Main linear growth of <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> (mm)		
		Microorganism against <i>F. oxysporum</i>	Control	* PGI %
Fungal isolate "H1" from AI Arish	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	11.66 j	90	87.04
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	13.00 j		85.64
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	20.00 fgh		77.86
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	56.33 a-d		37.41
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	56.66 a-d		37.04
Fungal isolate "I2" from AI Arish	<i>Trichoderma strigosum</i>	22.66 e-h	90	74.82
	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	18.66 hi		79.26
	<i>Trichoderma album</i>	23.00 e-h		74.44
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	60.66 a		32.60
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	54.66 bcd		39.35
L.S.D 0.01		5.54		

* PGI (Percent Growth Inhibition) = $\frac{\text{Colony growth in control plate} - \text{Colony growth in intersecting plate}}{\text{Colony growth in control plate}} \times 100$

- Each treatment represented the meaning of six replicates for two experiments.

Plate 1 The antagonistic effects of *Trichoderma strigosum* (A), *Trichoderma harzianum* (B), *Trichoderma album* (C), *Bacillus megaterium* (D) and *Bacillus subtilis* (E) against *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates (A₅, B₁, B₇, C₁ and C₂₄) from Bear AI Abd *in vitro* after 9 days of incubation.

Plate 1 The antagonistic effects of *Trichoderma strigosum* (A), *Trichoderma harzianum* (B), *Trichoderma album* (C), *Bacillus megaterium* (D) and *Bacillus subtilis* (E) against *Fusarium oxysporum* isolate (D₂) from Rafah and isolates (F₄₅, F₄₈, F₅₃ and F₅₈) from Al Arish *in vitro* after 9 days of incubation.

Plate 1 The antagonistic effects of *Trichoderma strigosum* (A), *Trichoderma harzianum* (B), *Trichoderma album* (C), *Bacillus megaterium* (D) and *Bacillus subtilis* (E) against *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates (G₁, H₁ and I₂) from Al Arish in vitro after 9 days of incubation.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study tested 13 isolates that matched with the specific primers (FOA₂₈-TL₃) to detect *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *albedinis*, the causal of Bayoud infection on date palm trees. Chemical fungicides and biological agents were evaluated for their inhibition of *Fusarium oxysporum* linear growth. Three commercial fungicides (Rizolex-T 50% WP, Tachigaren 30% SL, and Dithane M-45 80% WP) were chosen based on their efficacy for their wide control on other pathogens with increasing doses to identify the critical efficacy level that inhibit mycelial growth. The results showed that Tachigaren 30% SL had the significant effect on the linear growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates with 92.2%, 88.6%, and 80% to isolate I₂, A5, and G₁ respectively at 1000 ppm and 75.6%, 65.6%, and 61.1% to isolate I₂, G₁, H₁, and A5 respectively at 500 ppm. compared with Rizolex-T 50% and Dithane M-45 80%. Hymexazol in Tachigaren 30% SL interferes with the synthesis of RNA and DNA causes distortions, moreover. It has fungitoxic activity on fungal cells because of O-glucoside component. *Trichoderma* spp. showed that suppressive and mycoparasitic interaction with all *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates, *Trichoderma album* showed the highest inhibition rate on average 75% followed by 73% and 71.5% for *Trichoderma harzianum* and *Trichoderma strigosum* respectively. Conversely, *Bacillus* spp. showed a remarkable inhibition percentage with 40% on average for *Bacillus subtilis* with *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates, meanwhile, *Bacillus megaterium* had not significant effect on the pathogen mycelial growth.

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